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family business; small business, family farm; employment, welfare, taxes; "Fundamentals of the family business"; home-based work; family farm cluster, each family entrepreneur, family farm business.

Relevance of the topic.

Entrepreneurship, in particular, the development of family business is one of the key factors in ensuring the socio-economic development of the country in the digital economy. Because family business provides an opportunity to solve the problem of employment, reduce poverty; increase the welfare of the population.

In recent years, a number of measures have been taken to create a stable environment and a regular source of income for each family, such as radically improving the economic situation of the population, ensuring living standards and significant positive changes in it, and organizing entrepreneurship. provide systematic practical assistance in the

FAMILY BUSINESS AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the essence of the family business, the legal framework for organizing family business, the development of family business, and improving the family's welfare.

In addition, there are proposals for the development of family businesses in the country in the digital economy:

development and implementation of entrepreneurial initiatives, training of the population in entrepreneurial skills and practical assistance in organizing relevant events, creation of additional jobs and sources of income, organization of mini-clusters in newly engaged families, market infrastructure facilities, service and network of service points.

The adopted programs such as "Every family is an entrepreneur", "Youth is our future", "Prosperous village", and "Prosperous neighborhood" are aimed at providing employment and creating a source of income for families. In total, more than 13 trillion soums of soft loans have been allocated under the programs to cover more than 600,000 families.

Entrepreneurship approaches aimed at elucidating the concept of entrepreneurial activity

Authors	Definition	Source
Richard Cantillon	"Entrepreneur - a person with a lot of risk" (1969)	Cantillon Richard // Great Soviet Encyclopedia: [in 30 volumes] / ch. red. A. M.
Gofurov	to generate revenue based on production and services activity	U.V. Economic theory. Textbook.- T., 2007.-136 pages
F. F. Mamatov	He sees the concept of business as having a much broader meaning than the concept of entrepreneurship.	Mamatov F.F. Directions for improving the system of small business support based on a synergistic approach to development problems.-T.: Economics and Finance, 2008.- p.13.

It should be noted that in an administrative-command environment based on a planned economy, the family economy was considered mainly as a consumer entity in the economy. In the context of an innovative, digital economy, the family economy as a subject of microeconomics should be the object of major scientific research. However, the fact that the study of this problem has become a very responsible and vital necessity on the one hand, and their theoretical and practical solutions have not been adequately addressed, requires the study of some theoretical and methodological aspects of this issue.

This theoretical evidence is the basis for the following conclusion. First, the family economy has become a subject of microeconomics in a free economy based on market relations.

Second, as a business entity, the family has the right to own its own property, means of production, labor, and income

(profit) as a result of its activities. Social benefits can also be provided on the basis of family business. Take, for example, an entrepreneurial teacher or an entrepreneurial physician. They are constantly developing and improving their professions by improving their skills and gaining experience. They work thinking that it will benefit people more than improving their professional skills. Such activities can be financially and spiritually encouraged by community members.

Third, family business is also a unique business that relies on family property and the labor force of family members.

Finally, important conceptual directions for improving the well-being of the family are now not only ways to increase wages, but also to increase the income (profit) of family members by developing entrepreneurship, using property and increasing the efficiency of management.

One of the important aspects of improving the well-being of the family is to address its theoretical issues. However, the economic literature has not yet developed a definition of the concept of family well-being that fully meets today's requirements. Because of this, this problem is also one of the problems waiting to be solved.

Studies have shown that the establishment of family business solves many socio-economic problems in our country. First of all, it will create a class of small business and private entrepreneurs, which will be the main driving force of market relations, provide employment and increase the welfare of the population, create opportunities to enrich the country's market with consumer goods and various services. In return, it solves the problem of unemployment. However, family business does not develop on its own. It is necessary to develop it at the modern level, to bring it to a state of production of highly competitive products (works, services). This requires researching the theoretical and practical issues of the problem and developing appropriate recommendations for their improvement.

As of January 1, 2020, the number of family enterprises operating in the economy of Uzbekistan amounted to 24,137, their share in total operating commercial enterprises was 8.0%, their net income from sales of goods and services amounted to 679,320.3 million sums, their share in family income 55.2%, the number of jobs created due to them is 358.56 thousand.

It states that "a family business is a small business entity established by its participants on a voluntary basis for the

production and sale of goods, on the basis of share or common property of the participants, as well as the property of each of the participants."

It is known that Japan is one of the most developed countries in the field of small business. He has advanced experience in developing small businesses and family entrepreneurship. 99.7% of the total enterprises operating in the country, 70% of the total employed population, and more than 50% of the total value-added products are small businesses. Large corporations such as Toyota, Honda and Sony are also small. was one of the most highly developed countries to start operating as an enterprise.

As of January 1, 2020, the share of income from a small business in the total income of the population was 59.5%. In the structure of the total income of the population, the income from small businesses accounted for a significant share in Jizzakh (70.6%), Bukhara (65.6%), Samarkand (63.9%), and Surkhandarya (63.7%) regions.

According to the results of January-June 2020, 120 569.5 billion sums were spent by small businesses. The share of small businesses in the gross value added of the main sectors of the economy was 97.8% in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, and 74.9% in construction and services. 39.4% and 22.8% in industry.

Conclusions and suggestions

In the context of the digital economy, the following conclusions can be drawn about the development of family businesses in the country:

Information centers for start-ups provide information and guidance to start-ups, provide financial support through special

funds, and provide them with premises if necessary.

Citizens engaged in family business should have access to the latest scientific and innovative technologies

Today, family business registration is much simplified to further improve this process;

Support for foreign economic activity of family businesses, including the development of trade, scientific, technical and industrial relations with foreign countries;

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